

**AN INSIGHT TO SHARANGADHAROKTA KARMA IN BHAVAPRAKASHA
NIGANTOKTA DRAVYAS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO DEEPANA AND PACHANA**

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ABSTRACT

Pharmacological activities play a vital and vibrant role in pharmacotherapeutics. Karma is always interconnected with Chikitsa to understand, analyze mode of action. Sharangadhara explored 24 karmas which are specific, Chikitsa sahayaka, among them Deepana, pachana portray an important role. Charaka has envisaged Deepaniya dashemani, not mentioned Pachaniya Dashemani, there are various drugs in Bhavaprakasha nigantu, which are having Deepana, Pachana karmas, whereas Sharangadhara has mentioned limited number of drugs useful in the context of Deepana and Pachana Karma, but those drugs can be beneficial in many diseases. In this current paper effort has been put fourth to collect, and rationalize the drugs from Haritakyadi varga, Karpuradi varga, Guduchyadi varga of Bhavaprakasha nigantu for Deepana, Pachana Karma

KEYWORDS: Karma, Dravya, Deepana, Pachana, treatment

INTRODUCTION

The word karma is applied for any action or process or mechanism which has an outcome.

संयोगे च विभागे च कारणं द्रव्यमाश्रितम्।

कर्तव्यस्य क्रिया कर्म कर्म नान्यदपेक्षते॥

Karma is the entity in dravya which is responsible for samyoga and vibhaga is having samvayi sambandha which is inseparable with dravya and responsible for specific action. Sharangadhara has explained 24 oushada karmas which are responsible for the action of the Dravya among them Deepana Pachana play an important role in treatment. However in Sharangadhara Samhitha mentioned less number of drugs for these Karmas, In

Bruhatrayees like Charaka samhitha there is a mentioning of Deepaniya Dashemani, but no Pachaniya Dashemani. Bhavaprakasha nigantu mention Deepana, Pachana dravyas with their Gunakarmas. The drugs explained in Hareetakyadi, Guduchyadi, Karpooradi, varga, having the above Karmas are compiled and listed.

METHODOLOGY

The Sharangadharokta Karmas, Deepana and Pachana Karmas has been screened from Hareetakyadi, Karpooradi, Guduchyadi Vargas of Bhavaprakasha Nigantu, Botanical name, Family, Rasapanchaka, phytoconstituents, mode of action of Deepana, Pachana drugs has been

rationalized, keeping both ancient and modern views.

Deepana:

पचेत् न आमं वह्निकृच्च दीपनं तद्यता मिशि : ।

(शा.सं पू ४)

पचेदिति ।यदद्रव्यमामं न पचेद्ब्रह्मीकृच्च भवति तद्दीपनं

जानीयात् ।यथा मिशिः शतपुष्प। (आडमल्ल)

The drug which stimulates the digestive fire but does not digest ama is called Deepana.

Eg: Mishi, Ghritha

According to Adamalla, the karma involves increasing digestive fire is called Pachana,

Eg:Mishi

Pachamahabhutikatwa – Agni

Rasa –katu, Amla,Lavana.

Guna - Ushna,Tikshna.

BHAVAPRAKASHA NIGANTOKTA DEEPANA DRAVYAS

HARITAKYADI VARGA

Sanskrit name	Botanical name	Family	Rasapanchaka	Phytoconstituents
<p>Haritaki</p> <p>Part used: Fruit</p>	Terminalia chebula	Combretaceae	<p>Rasa: Lavana varjitha Pancharasa</p> <p>Guna:Laghu, ruksha</p> <p>Veerya:Ushna</p> <p>Vipaka:Madhura</p> <p>Karma: Tridosahara, Anulomana, Deepana, rasayana, chakshushya, Medhya, Brumhana etc</p>	Tannins, Chebulic acid, gallic acid etc
<p>Ardra</p> <p>Part used Rhizome</p>	Zingiber officinale	Zingiberaceae	<p>Rasa:Katu</p> <p>Guna: Guru, ruksha, Tikshna</p> <p>Veerya: Ushna</p> <p>Vipaka: Madhura</p> <p>Karma: Vata-Kaphahara, bhedana, Deepana rochana etc</p>	Zingiberene, Gingerol, Gingerin
<p>Pippali</p> <p>Part used: Fruit</p>	Piper longum	Piperaceae	<p>Rasa:Katu</p> <p>Guna:Laghu, ruksha</p> <p>Veerya:Ushna</p>	Piperine, Piplartine

			Vipaka:Madhura Karma: Deepana, vrishya, Rasayana, Shwasahara, krimighna, pleehaghna etc	
Pippali moola Part used:Root 	Piper longum	Piperaceae	Rasa:Katu Guna : Laghu, ruksha Virya: Ushna Vipaka: Katu Karma: Deepana, krimighna	Piperine, Piplartine
Maricha Part used: Fruit 	Piper nigrum	Piperaceae	Rasa:Katu Guna : Laghu, ruksha Virya: Ushna Vipaka: Katu Karma: Deepana, krimighna	Piperine, piperidine
Ajamoda Part used: Fruit 	Apium graveolens	Apiaceae	Rasa:Katu Guna : Laghu, ruksha Virya: Ushna Vipaka: Katu Karma: Deepana, krimighna	Umbuliferene, myristicic acid
Jeeraka Part used: Fruit a)Shwetha jeeraka 	Cuminum cyminum Carum carvi	Apiaceae Apiaceae	Rasa:Katu Guna : Laghu, ruksha Virya: Ushna Vipaka: Katu Karma: Deepana, krimighna	Cuminaldehyde, cuminic alcohol

<p>c)Kala ajaaji</p>	<p>Nigella sativa</p>	<p>Ranunculaceae</p>		
<p>Dhanyaka Part used: Fruit</p>	<p>Coriandrum sativum</p>	<p>Apiaceae</p>	<p>Rasa:Katu Guna : Laghu, ruksha Virya: Ushna Vipaka: Katu Karma: Deepana, krimighna</p>	<p>Eugenol, Coriondrol, fixed oils</p>
<p>Shatapushpa Part used: Fruit</p>	<p>Foeniculum vulgare</p>	<p>Apiaceae</p>	<p>Rasa:Katu Guna : Laghu, ruksha Virya: Ushna Vipaka: Katu Karma: Deepana, krimighna</p>	<p>Carvone, eugenol, etc</p>
<p>Methika Part used: Fruit</p>	<p>Trigonella foenum graecum</p>	<p>Apiaceae</p>	<p>Rasa:Katu Guna : Laghu, ruksha Virya: Ushna Vipaka: Katu Karma: Deepana, krimighna</p>	<p>Saponnins, diosgenin steroids etc</p>
<p>Hapusha Part used: Fruit</p>	<p>Juniperous communis</p>	<p>Cupressaceae</p>	<p>Rasa:Katu Guna : Laghu, ruksha Virya: Ushna Vipaka: Katu Karma: Deepana, krimighna</p>	<p>Geigerone, essential oils</p>

Vidanga Part used: Fruit 	Embelia ribes	Myrsnaceae	Rasa:Katu Guna : Laghu, ruksha Virya: Ushna Vipaka: Katu Karma: Deepana, krimighna	Embelin, quercitol, Embelic acid
Katuki Part used: Rhizome 	Picrorhiza kurroa	Scrophularaceae	Rasa: Tikta Guna:Laghu, ruksha Virya: Sheeta Vipaka: Katu Karma: Bhedana, deepana, Hrudyā	Picoside, Kutkin
Tejovathi Part used: Bark 	Zanthoxylu m alatum	Rutaceae	Rasa: Katu, tikta Guna:Laghu, ruksha Virya:Ushna Vipaka: Katu Karma:Shwasahara, Kasahara	Myrcene, Carvone
Bharangi Part used: Root, root bark 	Clerodendru m serratum	Verbenaceae	Rasa: Katu, Guna: Laghu, ruksha Virya: Ushna Vipaka: katu Karma: Karma: jwarahara, shothahara, Kasahara	Quercetin, Serratogenic acid
Ativisha	Aconitum heterophyllu	Ranunculaceae	Rasa: Tikta, katu Guna:	Atisin, Aconitic acid

Part used: Rhizome 	m		Laghu,ruksha Virya: Ushna Vipaka: Katu Karma:Krimighna , Kasahara,Atisarah ara	
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KARPOORADI VARGA

Sanskrit name	Botanical name	Family	Rasapanchaka	Phytoconstituents
1.Guggulu Part used: Resin 	Commiphora mukul	Burseraceae	Rasa: Katu, tikta, Kashaya, Madhura Guna: Vishada, ruksha Virya: Ushna Vipaka: Katu Karma: Brimhana, Vrishya (Nava guggulu) Lekhana(Puran guggulu)	Z-guggulosterone, E-guggulosterone etc
2.Jatiphala Part used: Aerial, fruit 	Myristica fragrans	Myristicaceae	Rasa: Tikta Guna: Tikshna Virya: Ushna Vipaka: katu Karma: Grahi, Swarya, Krumighna etc	Myristin, myristic acid
3.Lavanga Part used: Flower bud 	Syzigium aromaticum	Myrtaceae	Rasa: katu, tikta Guna: Laghu, ruksha Virya: Sheeta Vipaka: katu Karma: Kasahara, shwasahara etc	Euginine, eugenol
4.Musta Part used: Rhizome	Cyperus rotendus	Cyperaceae	Rasa: Katu, tikta Guna: Laghu,	Cyperlone, cyperol, rotundone

				ruksha Virya: Sheeta Vipaka: Katu Karma: Jwarahara, trishnahara, krimighna etc	
5.Karchura Part used: Rhizome 	Curcuma zeodoaria	Zingiberaceae		Rasa: Katu Guna: Laghu, ruksha Virya: ushna Katu: Katu Karma: shwasahara, kustahara etc	Camphene, borneol
7.Granthiparna Part used: Whole plant 	Polygonum aviculare	Polygonaceae		Rasa: Tikta Guna: Laghu, ruksha Virya: Sheeta Vipaka: Katu Karma: Jwarahara, trishnahara, krimighna etc	Polygonic acid

GUDUCHYADI VARGA

Sanskrit name	Botanical name	Family	Rasapanchaka	Phytoconstituents
Arka Part used: Leaves, latex 	Calatropis procera	Asclepidaceae	Rasa:Katu Guna: Laghu, ruksha Virya: Ushna Vipaka: katu Karma:Krimighna, vishaghna, pleehaghna,	Calatoxin, gigantins etc
Snuhi Part used: Latex	Euphorbia tirucalli L	Euphorbiaceae	Rasa:Katu Guna: Laghu, ruksha Virya: Ushna Vipaka: katu	Nerifolion, Euphol

			Karma:Krimighna, vishaghna, pleehaghna	
Shigru Part used: Leaves, flower, fruit 	Moringa oleifera	Moringaceae	Rasa: Katu Guna: Laghu, ruksha Virya: Ushna Vipaka: Katu Karma:Chakshushya , sangrahi, hrudhya, shukrala etc	Moringinine, quercetin,
Kutaja Part used: Bark, seed, fruit 	Holarrhena antidysenteric a (L.) Wall	Apocynaceae	Rasa:Tikta,Kashaya Guna: Laghu, ruksha Virya: Sheeta Vipaka: Katu Karma: Sangrahi, Arshaghna, Trishnaghna	Lupeol, holacetine
Apamarga Part used: Fruit, seed, whole plant 	Acharanthus aspera	Amaranthacea e	Rasa: Tikta, katu Guna: Laghu, ruksha Virya: Ushna Vipaka: Katu Karma: Rochana,Kapha medohara	Achyranthine, hentriocontane
Punarnava Part used: Whole plant 	Bohrevia diffusa	Nyctaginaceae	Rasa:Tikta Guna:Laghu, ruksha Virya:Sheeta Vipaka:Katu Karma: Grahi	Hentriacontane, Trianthemine

Pachana

-(शा.सं पू ४)

पचेत् आमं न वहनीं च कुर्यात् तद्धि पचनम्
नगकेशरवत् विद्यात् चित्रोदीपन पाचनः

The drugs which digest Ama but does not
stimulate Agni is pachana dravyas

Eg-Nagkeshara

पचत्यामंमित्यादि। यद्रव्यमामं पचति वह्निं न कुर्यात् तत्
पाचनं ज्ञेयम् । अत्रापि द्रव्यप्रभावो बोधव्यः

तच्च नागकेशरवद्विद्याज्जानीयात्। नागकेशरं
रुक्षमुष्णलघ्वामपाचम् इति। आमपाचनमिति
विरुक्षणम्।

Adamalla, given explanation in Deepika
commentary as the karma involves digestion
of ama, not stimulating the digestive fire is
pachana

Pachamahabhutikatwa– Agni

Rasa –katu, Amla,Lavana.

Guna - Ushna,Tikshna.

BHAVAPRAKASHA NIGANTOKTA PACHANA DRAVYAS

HARITAKYADI VARGA

Sanskrit name	Botanical name	Family	Rasapanchaka	Phytoconstituents
Shunti Part used: Rhizome 	Zingibera officinalis	Zingiberaceae	Rasa: katu Guna: Laghu, ruksha Virya: Ushna Vipaka: Madhura Karma: Pachana, dravashoshana etc	Zingiberene, Gingerol, Gingeri
Pippali moola Part used: Root 	Piper longum	Piperaceae	Rasa:Katu Guna:Laghu, ruksha Veerya:Ushna Vipaka:Madhura Karma: Deepana, vrishya, Rasayana, Shwasahara, krimighna, pleehaghna etc	Piperine, Piplartine

<p>Chitraka Part used: Root</p>	<p>Plumbago zeylanica</p>	<p>Plumbaginaceae</p>	<p>Rasa:Katu Guna:Laghu, ruksha Veerya:Ushna Vipaka: Katu Karma: Grahi, Kustaghna, krumighna</p>	<p>Plumbagin, Chitranone, Zeylanone</p>
<p>Yavani Part used: Fruit</p>	<p>Carum copticum</p>	<p>Apiaceae</p>	<p>Rasa:Katu Guna:Laghu, ruksha Veerya:Ushna Vipaka: Katu Karma:</p>	<p>Essential oils, Thymol</p>
<p>Jeeraka Part used: Fruit</p>	<p>Cuminum ciminum</p>	<p>Apiaceae</p>	<p>Rasa:Katu Guna:Laghu, ruksha Veerya:Ushna Vipaka: Katu Karma: ruchya, balya, medhya</p>	<p>Cuminaldehyde, cuminic alcohol</p>
<p>Dhanyaka Part used: Fruit</p>	<p>Coriandrum sativum</p>	<p>Apiaceae</p>	<p>Rasa:Tikta, Madhura Guna:Laghu, ruksha Veerya:Ushna Vipaka: Katu Karma:</p>	<p>Eugenol, Coriondrol, fixed oils</p>
<p>Shatapushpa Part used: Fruit</p>	<p>Anthem sowa</p>	<p>Apiaceae</p>	<p>Rasa:Tikta, Madhura Guna:Laghu, ruksha Veerya:Ushna Vipaka: Madhura Karma:</p>	<p>Carvone, thymol, coumarin</p>

<p>Hingu Part used: Resin</p>	<p>Ferula narthex</p>	<p>Apiaceae</p>	<p>Rasa:Katu Guna:Laghu, ruksha Veerya:Ushna Vipaka: Katu Karma: ruchya</p>	<p>Umbuliferine</p>
<p>Rasna Part used: Rhizome, leaves</p>	<p>Alpinia galanga</p>	<p>Zingiberacea e</p>	<p>Rasa:Tikta Gu`na:Guru Veerya: Ushna Vipaka: Madhura Karma:Vatahara,Kasa hara</p>	<p>Quercetin</p>
<p>Bharangi Part used: Root</p>	<p>Clerodendr um serratum</p>	<p>Verbinaceae</p>	<p>Rasa: Tikta, katu Guna:Laghu, ruksha Veerya: Ushna Vipaka: Katu Karma:Jwarahara, Kasahara, Krimighna</p>	<p>Hispidulin, scutellarin</p>
<p>Ativisha Part used: Rhizome</p>	<p>Aconitum heterophyll um</p>	<p>Ranunculacea e</p>	<p>Rasa: Katu,tikta Guna:Laghu, ruksha Veerya: Ushna Vipaka:Katu Karma:Grahi, Arshaghna</p>	<p>Atidine, atisine, heterophylline etc</p>
<p>Lashuna Part used: Rhizome</p>	<p>Alium sativam</p>	<p>Liliaceae</p>	<p>Rasas:katu, tikta, lavana, Kashaya, Madhura Guna: Snigdha, tikshna, picchila, guru, sara Virya: Ushna Vipaka: Katu Karma:krimighna, kustagna</p>	<p>Volatile oils, allin etc</p>

<p>Bhallataka Part used: Fruit</p>	Semicarpus anacardium	Anacardacea e	<p>Rasa: Katu, tikta Guna: laghu, snigdha Veerya: ushna Vipaka: katu Karma: rasayana, kustaghna</p>	Semicarpol, anacardic acid
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GUDUCHYADI VARGA

Sanskrit name	Botanical name	Family	Rasapanchaka	Phytoconstituents
<p>Bilwa Part used: Fruit, leaves, root</p>	Aegle marmelos	Rutaceae	<p>Rasa: Kashaya, tikta Guna: laghu, rukshas Veerya: ushna Vipaka: katu Karma: Grahi</p>	Essential oils, rutin, Marmisin
<p>Gambhari Part used: Fruit, root</p>	Gmelina arbora	Verbinaceae	<p>Rasa: madhura, tikta Guna: snigdha Veerya: ushna Vipaka: Madhura Karma: grahi, vatahara</p>	Gmelinol, arborone,
<p>Bruhati Part used: Root, fruit</p>	Solanum indicum	Solanaceae	<p>Rasa: tikta Guna: laghu, ruksha Veerya: ushna Vipaka: katu Karma: deepana, pachana</p>	Solanine, carpesterol
<p>Kantakari Part used: Root, fruit</p>	Solanum xanthocarpum	Solanaceae	<p>Rasa: tikta Guna: laghu, ruksha Veerya: ushna Vipaka: katu Karma:</p>	Solanocarpin, Solenin

			deepana, pachana, vatahara	
Asthisamhara Part used: Stem 	Cissus quadrangularis	Vitaceae	Rasa: Madhura, tikta Guna: guru, snigdha Veerya: sheeta Vipaka:Katu Karma: Sandhanakara	Gallic acid, Iridoides, Triterpenes

KARPURADI VARGA

Sanskrit name	Botanical name	Family	Rasapanchaka	Phytoconstituents
Lavanga Part used: Flower bud 	Syzgium aromaticum	Myrtaceae	Rasa: katu Guna:Laghu, ruksha Veerya: ushna Vipaka:katu Karma: deepana, pachana	Euginine, carophyllin, eugenol
Nagakeshara Part used: Fruit, flower 	Mesua fera	Guttiferae (Clusiaceae)	Rasa: Tikta Guna: laghu, ruksha Veerya: ushna Vipaka: katu Karma: Pachana, varnya etc	Mesuol, cyclohexodione
Usheera Part used: Roots 	Vetivera zezonoides	Graminae	Rasa:tikta Guna: laghu, snigdha Veerya: sheeta Vipaka: katu Karma	Allokhusiol, Vetiverol, Zizonol
Musta Part used: Rhizomes	Cyperus rotendus	Cyperaceae	Rasa:Tikta Guna:Laghu, ruksha	Cyperol, cyperlone, rotundone

Veerya:Sheeta
Vipaka:Katu
Karma:

Pharmacological action related to Deepana and Pachana:

Deepana dravyas are correlated with apperants, that which increase secretion of gastric juices and increases the appetite. Often corelated with carminatives, drugs which promote the expulsion of gases from the GIT and give a feeling of warmth and comfort in the epigastrium.

Pachana dravyas can be correlated to digistants, deepana pachana dravyas are corelated to stomachics in pharmacology. These are substances intended to promote digestion of food. A number of proteolytic, amylolytic and lipolytic enzymes are marketed in combination formulations and are vigorously promoted for dyspeptic symptoms, and as appetite stimulants or health tonics. They are occasionally beneficial, only when their elaboration in g.i.t. is deficient. These are drugs which promote the expulsion of gases from the g.i.t. and give a feeling of warmth and comfort in the epigastrium. Bitters stimulate the taste buds, Pachana reduce reflex secretion of gastric juices.

Used for: flatulent dyspepsia.

DISCUSSION

Deepana, Pachana are the two important pharmacological activities needed for Shodhana or pre biopurificatory measures, Sharangadhara has given utmost importance and elucidates initially. These are the common Karmas needed to increase Agni, bala and Rasayana. There is a need for Deepana & Pachana in almost all Sroto Vikaras. Sharangadhara mentioned Mishi (Anthem sowa), for Pachana, Nagakeshara (Mesua fera),

Chitraka for Deepana, Pachana. These are myriad of drugs like 28 drugs for Deepana, 22 Pachana and 4 Deepana pachana drugs from Hareetakyadi, Karpuradi and Guduchyadi varga. Deepana dravyas are of Katu rasa, ushna veerya, katu Vipaka, Laghu, ruksha guna predominance, Pachana dravyas are of Katu rasa, ushna veerya, ruksha, tikshna guna. Both Deepana, Pachana dravyas have katu rasa, ushna veerya, Katu vipaka, laghu, ruksha guna but Pachana dravyas are of Tikta rasa predominance. Deepana dravyas are rich in Volatile oils, terpenes. Pachana dravyas are rich in volatile oils, flavonoids etc. There is a need of Deepana and Pachana karmas for Doshavasechana, when there is amavastha, the disease is deeprooted, Deepana, Pachana and Deepana Pachana, Dravyas can be clinically utilized rationally, practically by retrospectively Bhavaprakasha nigantu and screening the 3 Vargas Viz Haritakyadi varga, Karpuradi varga, Guduchyadi varga.

CONCLUSION

Deepana (apparents), Pachana (digestants) are the core prime pharmacological activities needed to manage all the disorders clinically as Shodanartha and Shamanartha. The drugs of Bhavaprakasha nigantu from Haritakyadi, Karpuradi, Guduchyadi Varga to contribute majorly for Deepana, Pachana karma

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